

D5.1 Project image package

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 101120390

USE IPM

COVER PAGE

PROJECT	
Project number:	101120390
Project name:	Up-skilling researchers for sustainable entrepreneurship based on innovation process management
Project acronym:	USE IPM
Call:	HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-TALENTS-03
Topic:	HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-TALENTS-03-01
Type of Action:	HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions
Granting authority:	European Research Executive Agency
Project starting date:	fixed date: 1 July 2023
Project end date:	30 April 2027
Project duration:	46 months

Description	Project image package will include logo and web page of the project USE IPM. Additionally, this deliverable will present visual identity of the project that is shared on social media with a wider community. Using this document as a solid basis, the project participants will acknowledge EU funding and refer to the USE IPM project activities.
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Deliverable Name:	Project Image Package
Deliverable Number:	D5.1
Work Package:	WP5 – Dissemination and outreach activities
Dissemination Level:	P – Public
Due Date:	M03 – September 30, 2023
Completion Date:	M03 – September 25, 2023
Submission Date:	M03 – September 30, 2023
Deliverable Leader:	University of Tirana (UT)
Deliverable Author(s):	Sandra Milanovic

VERSIONING AND CONTRIBUTION HISTORY

Version	Date	Change History	Author(s)
1.0	20/09/2023	First version prepared by task leader	Sandra Milanovic (FEUN)
2.0	22/09/2023	Reviewed version	Elona Pojani (UT)
3.0	24/06/2023	Reviewed version	Sandra Milanovic (FEUN)
4.0	28/09/2023	Quality review	PC and SAB member
Final	30/09/2023	Final version submitted to the EC	Marija Radosavljevic (FEUN)

DISCLAIMER

This research is part of the 101120390 - USE IPM - HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-TALENTS-03-01 project, funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the European Research Executive Agency can be held responsible for them.

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ACRONYMS

Acronym	Full name
EU	European Union
EC	European Commission
PC	Project Coordinator

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1. INTRODUCTION

The USE IPM project got funding under the Horizon Europe call HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-TALENTS-03-01 under grant number 101120390. Therefore, the project image package is an important part of the project in order to disseminate and communicate its results and acknowledge EU funding received through the project. The most important parts of this document are the logo of the USE IPM project, the EU emblem, the project's website, social networks and templates. Through these kinds of tools, visitors get the first impression of the project and its purpose.

The most important dissemination tool is the project website which reflects the project activities. Moreover, the project will use social networks in order to get more advanced reach to the general public interested in the topic of sustainable entrepreneurship and innovation process management. Through its templates for PowerPoint presentations, agendas and similar the project partners will disseminate a given project funding.

2. LOGOS

As in the project are 12 partners, one coordinator, 10 partners and one associated entity, their logos will be stressed in every document used for the USE IPM project purposes (Table 1).

Table 1: List of the USE IPM project participants and their logos

Number	Short name	Legal name	Country	Logo
1	FEUN	FACULTY OF ECONOMICS NIS	RS	
2	UT	UNIVERSITETI I TIRANES	AL	
3	UBL	UNIVERZITET U BANJOJ LUCI	BA	
4	USK	Ss. CYRIL AND METHODIUS UNIVERSITY IN SKOPJE	MK	
5	OCom	OPENCOM I.S.S.C	IT	

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6	SME4	SME4SPACE VZ	BE	
7	ALDA	ALDA - ASSOCIATION EUROPEENNE POUR LA DEMOCRATIE LOCALE	FR	
8	IIE	MEDUNARODNI INSTITUT PODUZETNISTVA	HR	
9	UNIVPM	UNIVERSITA POLITECNICA DELLE MARCHE	IT	
10	UAlg	UNIVERSIDADE DO ALGARVE	PT	
11	UMA	UNIVERSIDAD DE MALAGA	ES	
12	ISPIM	THE INTERNATIONAL SOCIETY FOR PROFESSIONAL INNOVATION MANAGEMENT LTD	UK	

Source: Authors' presentation.

Secondly, for the project's visual identity creation it was developed a logo for the project named "UP-SKILLING RESEARCHERS FOR SUSTAINABLE ENTREPRENEURSHIP BASED ON INNOVATION PROCESS MANAGEMENT" whose acronym is the USE IPM (Figure 1).

Figure 1: USE IPM logo

Source: Authors' presentation.

In the logo, the project acronym is stipulated, while the light as one of the symbols in the logo is the representation of entrepreneurship that is widely used in the practice. Three lines represent innovation process management, while the green leaf and green colour in the logo present a sustainable aspect of the project. The logo was chosen by the voting of all project partners by a majority rule.

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Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

**Funded by
the European Union**

**Funded by
the European Union**

The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text.

Accordingly, the USE IPM project uses:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 101120390.

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information. Moreover, it must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

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3. PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS

To promote the USE IPM project through tangible promotional material, during the kick-off meeting of the project roll-up (Figure 2) the project was used and individual promo material was shared with meeting participants. This material will be continuously shared during the most important meetings and events of the project and in line with the budget for these purposes. All materials will be produced in British English and if necessary, translated to other European languages based on the purpose of the specific dissemination material.

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Faculty of Economics

Project number: 101120390 Project acronym: USE IPM
Call: HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-TALENTS-03

Figure 2: USE IPM roll-up
Source: Authors.

Promo material includes following items (Figure 3):

- small reusable bag,
- aluminum reusable bottle,
- notebook,
- mix of pen, sticky notes, ruler and holder,
- wireless phone charger.

Figure 3: Pictures of the USE IPM promo material

Source: Authors.

On every item of promo material logo of the project and acknowledgement of the EU funding are printed. Also, while making the final composition of the project promo material, ecology and sustainability were the main priorities. Therefore, reusable items and items from the natural materials were selected.

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4. WEBSITE

For the USE IPM project implementation purposes, the website www.useipm.com will be continuously updated with project general information, news, deliverables, publications, consortium information, and complementary content to provide visitors with a broad idea of the project concept and the progress of the activities.

During the first month of the project (July 2023), the USE IPM website was launched (Figure 4). The hosting of the website is based at the Faculty of Economics Nis and the envisaged website lifetime is project duration plus five years after the project completion.

The landing page of the project contains the project logo and the main details about the project that could attract the attention of the visitors. Hence, minimalism and distinctive colours in the theme of the project were selected. Dominantly, green and white colours were used.

A three-sections approach is applied in the website design. At the very beginning, the website has links to social media channels such as Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn and X. In the second line, home, about, project partners, community of interest, news, and search buttons are added. The middle part of the page is dedicated to the folding photos and leading priorities of the project. The bottom part of the website contains the EU funding acknowledgement and one-click links to social media and tabs of the web site.

Figure 4: Landing page of the USE IPM project

Source: Authors' presentation.

The “About” button branches to the tabs explaining the project’s objectives, methodology, implementation and envisaged impact through the project lifetime.

The “Partners” button depicts three types of project partners. By clicking on every tab, visitors can see that there are non-academic partners of the project, partners from widening countries and academic EU partners.

The “Community of interest” button is under construction and depends on the next project’s activities and the signing of agreements with interested parties that also want to participate in the project’s activities.

The “New” button will be made of a collection of relevant articles, event information, researcher’s activities and the like.

The “Results” button gives an overview of what results are expected during the project.

The project website will be filled with the data in the following months as the project activities continue to grow and the first results appear. After the establishment of a database of innovative solutions created under the EI centres, they will be uploaded to the website after anonymization.

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5. SOCIAL MEDIA ACCOUNTS

Dissemination and Communication are vital parts of every project activity. Besides communication between all parties involved in the USE IPM project implementation such as EC, PC, and other project partners (beneficiaries and associated partners), communication to the external wider community is also a vastly important part. All social media accounts will use hashtags #useipm, #horizon and #horizoneurope.

5.1. Facebook

Facebook page could be found on the following link: <https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61550306741616> (Figure 5).

Figure 5: USE IPM Facebook page

Source: Authors' presentation.

USE IPM project Facebook page is already launched and it is gaining followers on the day-to-day basis. On this page, followers can follow USE IPM activities more closely.

5.2. Instagram

Instagram profile of the USE IPM project can be found on the following link: <https://www.instagram.com/useipm/>.

Figure 6: USE IPM Instagram page

Source: Authors' presentation.

Instagram page is developed to reach population that is not using Facebook, since USE IPM project targets wider audience with different age and content preferences.

5.3. LinkedIn

LinkedIn page can be found on the following link: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/use-ipm-project/>.

Figure 7: USE IPM LinkedIn page

Source: Authors' presentation.

LinkedIn page is created with the aim that researchers involved in the project could refer to this project as own career milestone and, in that way, to promote project activities. Also, LinkedIn page serves to engaging business community of interest and to attract attention of stakeholders willing to involve in the project activities.

5.4. X (previously Twitter)

X (previously Twitter) account of the USE IPM project can be found on the following link: https://twitter.com/useipm_project.

Figure 8: USE IPM X account

Source: Authors' presentation.

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6. TEMPLATES

In order to provide the uniformity of the outputs and to facilitate the internal and external communication, templates for different kind of documents (including for presentations (PowerPoint) are available for all project partners. Templates are available to project team in the USEIPM's management platform (i.e., "USE IPM project" folder on Google drive and "USE IPM project" as Trello workspace) with access allowed only to the project partners. The project logo must also be included in all the documents related to the project as well as acknowledgement of EU funding received for the project. Templates that will be used for the project image presentation are template for agenda and PowerPoint presentation. Through these documents project members will try to attract attention of a wider community.

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Project number: 101120390

**Project name: UP-SKILLING RESEARCHERS FOR SUSTAINABLE ENTREPRENEURSHIP
BASED ON INNOVATION PROCESS MANAGEMENT**

Project acronym: USE IPM

Call: HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-TALENTS-03

Topic: HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-TALENTS-03-01

Type of action: HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions

Granting authority: European Research Executive Agency

KICK-OFF MEETING AGENDA

13-14 July, 2023

**Faculty of Economics, University of Nis, Serbia
Trg kralja Aleksandra Ujedinitelja 11, 18000 Nis, Republic of Serbia**

USEIPM Project is inviting you to a scheduled Zoom meeting.

Topic: Kick-off Meeting

Time: Jul 13, 2023 09:30 AM Belgrade, Bratislava, Ljubljana

Every day, 2 occurrence(s)

Jul 13, 2023 09:30 AM

Jul 14, 2023 09:30 AM

Join Zoom Meeting

<https://us06web.zoom.us/j/84313479320?pwd=RkxpR2lqemlJN0N3SzF4R2FLRjhHQ09>

Meeting ID: 843 1347 9320

Passcode: 956513

Thursday, 13 July, 2023

Time	Topic	Presenter
Part I Introduction session		
09 ³⁰ – 10 ⁰⁰	Registration of participants	
10 ⁰⁰ – 10 ¹⁵	Kick-off meeting welcome and opening speech	Marija Radosavljevic, PhD, Project coordinator; Tadija Djukic, PhD, Dean of FEUN Biljana Djordjevic, PhD, Vice Dean of FEUN

Figure 9: USE IPM project's agenda (example)

Source: Authors' presentation.

An example of event/meeting agenda is given in Figure 9. Except logos of the USE IPM project partners and info about the project, the agenda describes in detail planned activities and their timing for the general public or interested parties of the project. Using event agenda, the USE IPM project will attract attention of stakeholders interested in the sustainable entrepreneurship based on innovation process management.

a) the first slide

b) the title slide

c) the middle slide

d) the last slide

Figure 10: USE IPM ppt presentation (example)

Source: Authors' presentation.

A specific power point presentation template has been designed to be used in internal meetings and for the project's presentation in dissemination events. The power point presentation includes the logo of the project, the logo of the EU (indicating that the project is funded by the EU), specific format for fonts and titles, and a frame and colours that identify the USE IPM project (as shown in Figure 10).

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7. CONCLUSION

The project image package is developed with the one purpose and that is to successfully disseminate and communicate the USE IPM project results. The project partners will follow the instructions given in this and, also, other deliverables in order to bring project results closer to both scientific and general public. Lastly, the project consortium will align its dissemination and communication activities to the GDPR regulations especially in the area of personal information processing (i.e., names).¹

¹ Under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU) 2016/679, USE IPM consortium has a legal duty to protect any information collected from persons involved in the project. Information contained in this document and any attachments may be privileged or confidential and intended for the exclusive use of the original recipient.

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REFERENCES

1. Grant Agreement - Project 101120390-USE IPM (2023).

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ANNEX

Reviews of the D5.1 Project Image Package

Review 1	
Revier Name:	Nenad Stojanovic, SAB member
Date of review:	28/09/2023
Reviewer opinion: (150 words)	The deliverable “Project package image” is in the line with the Grant Agreement for the project No. 101120390. It is well written and structured. Except two small formatting corrections, there is no need for further improvements of the deliverable by writer and other partners of the USE IPM consortium. General opinion: accepted; Comments: two minor comments regarding the language and text format.
Review 2	
Revier Name:	Marija Radosavljevic, PC
Date of review:	24/09/2023
Reviewer opinion: (150 words)	The deliverable “Project package image” is in the line with the Grant Agreement for the project No.101120390. It is well written and comprehensive. The deliverable efficiently presents project’s web site, as well as presence of the project in social media. General opinion: accepted; Comments: No.